

Osteomyelitis of The Left Humerus with Secondary Septic Arthritis of the Shoulder Joint in Neonate: A Case Report

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Abstract:- The presence of acute osteomyelitis and septic arthritis are uncommon in neonate. Recognition and treatment of adjacent septic arthritis is a matter of urgency and importance, as it may result in severe sequelae such as sepsis, joint destruction and growth failure if it is not diagnosed and treated promptly.

In this paper we report a case of a 21-days-old neonate girl presented with left humeral osteomyelitis and secondary septic arthritis of the shoulder joint following hepatitis B vaccination. She received medical treatments including supportive care, antibiotics and a surgical drainage procedure.

The 3 months follow-up shows sclerotic changes to the proximal humerus in radiograph examination, without clinical manifestation. A long follow up of 1 – 2 years is required to detect all possible sequelae.

Keyword:- Osteomyelitis, Neonate, Septic Arthritis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Septic arthritis of the shoulder joint in the pediatric population is a rare condition, with a prevalence of 3-5 % of all septic joint. (1).

Septic arthritis of the shoulder joint might occur simultaneously with humeral osteomyelitis, particularly in children younger than 2 years of age, whose transphyseal vessels are instrumental in spreading infection. In addition, the joint capsule extends beyond epiphyseal plate in younger neonates, permitting easier hematogenous spread from metaphysis to adjacent joint space (2).

Early diagnosis and treatment are crucial. Delays in diagnostic and treatment could result in disastrous complications, including sepsis, destruction of the articular cartilage and the underlying epiphysis, loss of adjacent growth plate and dislocation of joint. These conditions might hinder neonates' movement and cause growth failure in the future (3,4,5).

The aim of this paper is to present a case of neonate humeral osteomyelitis with secondary septic arthritis of the shoulder joint and to highlight our diagnostic and therapeutic approach to this disease.

II. CASE REPORT

We present a case of 21-days-old neonate girl who presented to the pediatric emergency department with swelling and decreasing movement of the upper left arm since the last 9 days after receiving Hepatitis type B vaccine. The patient also presented with a mild fever since the last 9 days. She had been delivered spontaneously, 3100 g in weight and 49 cm in length.

The patient was active and alert, with a mild fever of 37.3 degree Celsius. Physical examination revealed swelling and redness of the left shoulder joint. There was decreasing movement of the left shoulder joint as well.

Plain radiograph showed a widening of shoulder joint space, periosteal reaction and lytic lesion along the left humerus. Laboratory result revealed increase level of leucocyte (36.42) and low level of hemoglobin (9.0). CRP was 90 and ESR was 30-42. A D10 0,18% fluids were administered in the Emergency room. Sultamicillin and Cloxacillin was given via an IV drip. The child was admitted to the pediatric ward and was treated by a pediatrician for 5 days. No significant clinical nor laboratory improvement were achieved, thus orthopedic consult was made.

Fig 1:- Clinical appearance of the left shoulder joint

III. DISCUSSION

Septic arthritis in neonates is rare and can be difficult to diagnose. The classic presentation of septic arthritis is the presence of acutely swollen, red, painful joint with limited motion and fever (6). The presence of pseudo paralysis in neonates is a crucial warning symptom of joint or bone infection (7). Though according to some studies, fever is not always present as the common signs of sepsis in neonates, thus careful clinical assessment is needed. (7,8). In this case, the patient presented with swelling, pain, limited movement of upper left arm and shoulder, accompanied by mild fever.

This patient received Hepatitis B vaccination that was administered intramuscularly on the deltoid muscle. It could be argued that in our case shoulder joint infection is due to contamination caused by poorly disinfected skin prior to injection. Thinner patients, in our cases a neonate, has a higher risk of bursal penetration, that could lead to osteomyelitis and septic arthritis (9).

Laboratory tests are necessary to help confirm the diagnosis of osteomyelitis and septic arthritis in neonates. The role of CRP as a diagnostic marker for neonatal sepsis has been widely studied and analyzed. Only a low amount of CRP passes through the placenta, making a slight rise in serum CRP in neonates always represent endogenous synthesis, with serum concentration rising above 5 mg/l in 6 hours, and peaking at 48 hours (10).

Although CRP has a particularly low sensitivity in the early stage of disease, its sensitivity increases when performed in a serial manner. Serial CRP measurement, combined with clinical status, is useful to monitor treatment response (10). According to a study by Zhan, et al (11), most neonates with osteomyelitis showed higher levels of WBC and CRP, which also present in this case. In our case, the blood work shows an elevated CRP of 90 mg/l. This along with the clinical presentation of the patient strongly indicates the presence of joint or bone infection.

At 2 weeks follow-up, clinical symptoms and lab result had improved significantly, with CRP serum level at 5.7 mg/l. This indicates that the patient's response to treatment was sufficient.

Management of septic arthritis in neonates remains controversial. A retrospective study by Gao et al stated that surgical intervention results in better outcomes with higher rate of full recovery, shorter course of intravenous antibiotics and better shoulder ROM compared to conservative approach (12). However, another study concluded that a conservative approach might be more beneficial for patients whose diagnosis and treatment had been delayed for 2 weeks (13).

We decided to perform a surgical exploration and debridement for our patient despite the 2 weeks delay, considering no sign of clinical and laboratory improvement after 5 days of conservative treatment, in order to obtain isolated pathogen and prevent further damage of bone and cartilage.

Fig 2:- Plain X-ray of the left humerus and shoulder joint.

The decision was taken to perform arthrotomy of the left shoulder immediately after taking informed consent from the parents. A deltopectoral approach was used to expose the shoulder joint and the proximal humerus. The area was thoroughly debrided. Necrotic bone and tissue were removed. Pus was drained and sent for culture and sensitivity.

Pus culture result was positive for *Staphylococcus aureus* which were sensitive to clindamycin, erythromycin, gentamicin, linezolid, oxacillin, rifampicin and vancomycin. Cloxacillin was then given as the antibiotic of choice.

After 2 weeks the lab results had improved significantly (Leu 16,010 and CRP 5.7). Surgical wound was nicely healed. The patient presented no sign of fever. Clinical examination showed no joint swelling nor tenderness.

The clinical examination on final follow-up at 3 months showed full range of motion present on both shoulder joints comparable. Radiologic follow-up shows sclerotic changes to the proximal humerus.

Fig 3:- Plain X-ray of the left humerus and shoulder joint at 3 months follow-up

IV. CONCLUSION

Acute osteomyelitis with secondary septic arthritis of the shoulder joint in neonates is uncommon. Timely diagnosis and prompt treatment are quintessential to prevent complications. Decision to open the joint should be taken as soon as the conservative treatment failed to relieve the symptoms and intraarticular pressure to prevent the ischemic bony changes.

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